

EDUCATORS' MENTAL HEALTH STATE, COPING MECHANISMS AN EDUCATIONAL MILIEU IN THE DISTANCE MODE OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted the Philippine educational system, necessitating a shift from traditional face-to-face learning to alternative teaching modalities such as modular, online, radio-based, and TV-based instruction. This study investigates the mental health state, coping mechanisms, and educational milieu of elementary teachers in Cluster 6 of the City Division of Ilagan during the pandemic. Data were gathered from 87 permanent teachers using questionnaires and unstructured interviews, analyzed through frequency and percentage distribution, weighted arithmetic mean, F-test, and Pearson r. Findings indicate that most teachers do not exhibit significant signs of depression, stress, or anxiety. However, those who do primarily employ problem-focused, emotion-focused, and avoidance strategies to cope. Significant differences in mental health and coping mechanisms were found when grouped by age, civil status, teaching position, and other demographic factors. Additionally, teachers' perceptions of their educational milieu in terms of safety, support, engagement, and connectedness were generally positive, though varied significantly across different profiles. The study concludes that while the majority of teachers maintain a normal mental state, ongoing support and policy review are essential to address the mental health challenges posed by the new educational context. Recommendations include sustained mental health initiatives, continued education on coping mechanisms, and further research on the impact of these mechanisms on teachers' mental well-being.

Keywords: *Mental Health, Educational Milieu, Coping Mechanism, Distance Learning*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine educational system is facing a challenging scenario brought about by the big change in educational process due to the pandemic. The Department of Education has to address these changes especially in delivery of teaching modalities since the traditional face to face interaction was prohibited resulting to difficulties in extending learning information and instructions affecting the teachers, the learners and the community.

The Bureau of Curriculum Development- Curriculum Standard Division in collaboration with the Assessment Curriculum and Technology Research Centre (ACTRC) has reduced and focused only on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Modified guidelines, policies and technological teaching modalities have been introduced to meet the demand of the new normal way of education. Some teaching modalities used are modular learning, online learning, Radio-Based Instruction and TV-based Instruction considering the synchronous and asynchronous way of learning.

The abrupt adjustment in the teaching delivery mode caused difficulties among the teaching force which affect their health mentally, physically, socially, financially, and psychologically.

Majority of the learners use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable in the context of the learner, and other learning resources activity sheets, study guides and other study materials. Learners can have access to electronic copies of learning materials on USB storage and printed SLMs. The teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners by checking their work submitted/dropped off at school every end of the week. The learners may ask assistance from the teacher via e-mail, telephone, text message/instant messaging, etc. during teacher's office hours, thus this modality allows the learners to learn in their own pace and in their convenient time. Aside from the modules given by the Regional office, crafting of radio-scripts, designing learning activity sheets and self-paced learning modules to meet the modified most essential learning competencies affects the mental status of the teachers especially in meeting the deadline for quality assurance. After designing and approval of the needed learning materials, these modules will be printed and reproduced hundreds of copies. Sorting the modules comes next followed by delivering the learning package to the learners who preferred modular learning modality. This situation affects the teachers physically.

One study stated that adjustment to new policies, guidelines, strategies or even the practices is a challenge to all the teachers nowadays. In October 2020, the Canadian Teachers' Federation *CTF/FCE* (2022) released the *CTF/FCE Canadian Teachers Responding to Coronavirus (COVID-19) – Pandemic Research Study Mental Health Report*. This document is an important baseline for understanding the impacts of teaching during a pandemic, and supports needed for teacher mental health as the COVID-19 pandemic unfolds. The *CTF/FCE Pandemic Study Phase One Survey* was conducted June 1-18, 2020, and had over 15,000 completed teacher responses. From

the results of this initial Survey, CTF/FCE reported on the mental health of students and teachers, and documented concerning mental health trends, as educators navigated emergency remote teaching in June 2020. This report revealed that the mental health of teachers was “severely endangered” by stressors such as: excessive workload, lack of clear directions and planning, increased screen time, and social isolation. The results also demonstrated that teachers were struggling to maintain work-life balance and did not have the time to properly attend to their personal physical well-being.

The challenges in the new normal put the teacher’s mental health really at stake. The teachers in Cluster 6 of the Schools Division of the City Division of Ilagan are not an exempted from experiencing these challenges. The researcher who belongs to the said cluster finds it timely to determine the mental health state of the teachers and how they cope with it. Based on observation and testimonies given, teachers in the grass-root level have to go to their students’ homes to bring the learning materials, spending from their own pocket and some have to cross rivers and climb mountain. Having the health at stake due to COVID, teachers need also to mingle with different kind of people and should maintain their patience when it comes to parent complaints and rants about the educational process. Teachers really need to adjust to meet the “no child left behind” policy of the Department of Education. This kind of educational setting triggers the mental health condition of the teachers especially that there is an immediate change leading them to get out from their teaching comfort zone. These situations disturb the physical, financial, and social aspect of the teachers.

The result of the present study will be a cornerstone of possible interventions which will possibly result in motivated, inspired and committed teachers.

Research Questions

The study investigated the educators’ mental health state, coping mechanisms, and educational milieu during the distance mode of learning in Cluster 6 in the City Division of Ilagan during this pandemic.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teachers according to:
 - a. Age
 - b. Civil status
 - c. Place of residence
 - d. Position
 - e. Grade level handled
 - f. Subjects handled
 - g. Number of years in teaching
2. What is the mental health state of the respondents?
3. Is there a significant difference in the mental health state of the respondents when grouped according to profile?
4. What coping mechanisms do the teachers employ in terms of:
 - a. problem-focused

- b. emotion- focused
 - c. Avoidance
5. Is there a significant difference in the coping mechanism employed by the respondents when grouped according to profile?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' mental health state and coping mechanism that they employed?
 7. What is the educational Milieu in the respondents' place of work as perceived by them in term of:
 - a. Safety
 - b. Support
 - c. Engagement
 - d. Connectedness
 8. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' perception in educational milieu when group according to profile?
 9. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' perception of educational milieu and mental health state of the respondents?
 10. Is there a significant relationship between the perception on educational milieu and coping mechanism employed by them?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive survey method of research was used in the study. The method aids the researcher to describe the nature of a situation on gathered information and conditions. In this support, Good and Scates Carter (1954), stated that descriptive method oftentimes characterized as a survey or nominative approach as it is used to look for insights into factors or conditions that are prevailing or existing. The descriptive survey method was used in this study to gather information and conditions on the mental health state and coping mechanism of teachers and their educational milieu in the distance mode of learning.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study were 87 elementary school teachers who are officially employed with permanent status in Cluster 6, Ilagan North District in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, for the school year 2021-2022. The researcher utilized the total population of the cluster 6 teaching workforce.

Table 1
Distribution of Teacher Respondents

School	Frequency	Percentage
Balla Elementary School	5	5.75
Capellan Elementary School	17	19.54

Manaring Integrated School	15	17.24
San Juan- Rugao Elementary School	17	19.54
San Lorenzo Integrated School	9	10.34
San Pablo-Quimalabasa Elementary School	5	5.75
San Rodrigo Elementary School	5	5.75
Tangcul-San Isidro Elementary School	14	16.09
Total	87	100

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher made use of the questionnaire, the standardized Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS) and the Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced (COPE) and interview to gather the data needed for the study.

Questionnaire. The questionnaire was used to get data on teachers' profile and their perception on their educational milieu, mental health state, and the coping mechanisms they employ in problems experienced. The questionnaire is composed of four (4) parts.

Part 1 sought to determine the profile of the respondents, specifically their age, sex, civil status, position, and number of years in service.

Part II I intended to find out the mental health state of the respondents using the DASS-21. This is a 21-item checklist with a set of three self-report scales designed to measure the emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress.

Part III sought to find out the Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced (COPE). It has three areas with twenty-eight items to discover the coping mechanisms of the respondents particularly those that are problem-focused, emotion-focused and avoidance strategies.

Part IV has 39 items to determine the educational milieu of the respondents. It is subdivided into four factors which is the safety, support, engagement, and connectedness.

Unstructured Interview. This was used to support the data gathered for deeper analysis.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first sought the permission of the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. After permission was granted the researcher coordinated with the school heads in cluster 6 for the floating of the questionnaire using the Google Form as a platform for gathering data from the respondents who have restrictions due to the

prevailing situation brought by the pandemic. For respondents who do not have restrictions, the researcher personally floated the questionnaire to them. The researcher also conducted interview which was done through phone calls and video calls for respondents who are restricted by the covid-19 virus and a face to face interaction with the respondents who have no restrictions.

Data were retrieved, tabulated, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data for each of the questions raised in the study, the following statistics were used:

Frequency and Percentage Count. To analyze the profile of the respondents, the frequency and percentage distribution were used. The standard scoring of the DASS 21 was used to determine the Mental health of the respondents;

Weighted Mean. In assessing the coping mechanisms of the respondents, the weighted average mean was used based on the standardized scoring of Brief- COPE. This was also used to analyze the teachers' perception on the educational milieu.

F-test. This was utilized to find out if there is a significant difference in the mental health condition of the respondents, their perception on the educational milieu and the coping mechanisms they employ when grouped according to their profiles.

Pearson-r. This was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the mental health condition and the coping mechanisms of the respondents and if there is a significant relationship between the respondents' educational environment and coping mechanisms.

Data Analysis Procedure

To interpret the result of the data gathered the following scoring guide were used:
Mental Health State

Mental Health State	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
	Score	Score	Score
Normal	0-9	0-7	0-14
Mild	10-13	8-9	15-18
Moderate	14-20	10-14	19-25
Severe	21-27	15-19	26-33
Extremely Severe	28+	20+	34+

Coping Mechanism

Scale	Qualitative Description
4	I've doing this a lot
3	A medium amount
2	A little bit
1	I haven't been doing this at all

Educational Milieu

Scale	Qualitative Description
3.25 -4.00	Very Much
2.50- 3.24	Much
1.75- 2.49	Not so much
1.00- 1.74	Not at all

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the teachers according to:
 - a. Age

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Age

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
21-25	6	6.90
26-30	20	22.99
31-35	19	21.84
36-40	10	11.49
41-45	14	16.09
46-50	9	10.34
51- 55	7	8.05
56-60	2	2.30
Total	87	100.00

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their age profile. It is revealed that there are 20 or 22.99 percent who belongs to age bracket 26-30, 19 or 21.84 percent for 31-35 age bracket, 14 or 16.09 percent under 41-45 bracket, 10 or 11.49 percent are within the ages of 36-40, nine or 10.34 are aged 46-50, seven or 8.05 percent are within the 51-55 age bracket, six or 6.90 percent are 21-25 years old and two or 2.30 percent belong to the 56-60 age bracket.

This implies that almost half of the respondent teachers are in their middle adulthood and a quarter in their late adulthood and more than a fourth are in their early adulthood.

b. Civil Status

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	20	22.99
Married	65	74.71
Widowed	2	2.30
Total	87	100.00

The frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to civil status is shown in Table 3. Data shows that 65 or 74.71 percent of the teacher respondents are married, 20 or 22.99 percent are single and two or 2.30 percent are widowed. Based from the table presented, most of the respondents are married.

In a study conducted by Cotten (1999) on marital status and mental health, she noted that marital status is often included as a control variable in mental health studies with two categories: married and unmarried. She further said that “being married are embedded in a network such as spouse, in laws, possibility of children, etc. and that these network members provide a variety of function which influence an individual’s sense of self and his or her resulting well-being.”

c. Place of Residence

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Place of Residence

Place of Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Home- based	34	39.08
Not-home based	53	60.92
Total	87	100.00

Based from Table 4 on the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to the place of residence, there are 53 or 60.92 percent who are not home-based and 34 or 39.08 percent who are home-based. This shows that the workplace of most of the respondents is outside of the area where they reside.

Teachers who are not homebased experience difficulties in performing their duties and responsibilities as teachers. Based on an interview with the teachers, they claim that they usually wake up early to prepare their things to be in the school before the class starts. Added to these is the dilemma on transportation to include fare hike during this pandemic and traveling also eats their time. Aside from these, traveling also affects their physical and emotional aspects. One of the respondents said “*yun bang haggard na*

haggard ka na pagdating sa school kasi andami mong bitbit tapos open-air pa, maalikabok. Kaya kahit anong ayos mo, malulukot pa rin ang damit mo at mawawala sa ayos ang buhok mo.” (You look haggard when you reach school because you have a lot of stuff to carry. It is very dusty because the vehicle that you are riding on is open. That is why no matter how tidy you are, your clothes get crumpled, and your hair is messy.) Another respondent also stated *”hindi mo rin mapigilan magdasal habang nasa býahe ka kasi hindi naman ikaw ang driver at hindi mo rin alam kung ligtas ka.” (You cannot help praying while you are travelling because you are not the driver, and you don’t know if you are really safe.)* Chances are, teachers who are into these situations possibly experience disappointments, stress and frustrations. Though most of the respondents attest that they are already accustomed to their daily routine.

d. Position/Rank

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Position

Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	15	17.24
Teacher II	6	6.90
Teacher III	52	59.77
Master Teacher I	12	13.79
Master Teacher II	2	2.30
Total	87	100.00

The frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to position/rank is presented in Table 5. The table reveals that there are 52 or 59.77 percent hold the position of Teacher III, 15 or 17.24 percent have Teacher I position, 12 or 13.79 are Master Teacher I, six or 6.90 o are Teacher II, and two or 2.30 percent are Master Teacher II.

It implies that majority or around 84 percent of the respondents have the rank of Teacher 1 - Teacher III and only about 16 percent have an item of master teacher.

e. Grade Level Handled

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Grade Level Handled

Grade Level Handled	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 1	16	18.39
Grade II	14	16.09
Grade III	12	13.79

Grade IV	9	10.34
Grade V	12	13.79
Grade VI	9	10.34
Multigrade	6	6.90
Total	87	100.00

Table 6 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to the grade level they handle. The data shows that most of the respondents are teaching Grade I with a frequency of 16 or 18.39. There are 14 or 16.09 percent who are teaching Grade II and 12 or 13.79 percent are teaching in Grade III and same number of teachers teaches Grade V. There are nine or 10.34 percent each in Grade level of IV, VI and Kindergarten. Only six or 6.90 percent handle multi-grade classes.

f. Subject Handled

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Subject Handled

Subjects Handled	Frequency	Percentage
All Subjects	72	82.76
Science, AP, ESP	4	4.60
Math, AP	8	9.20
EPP, MAPEH	3	3.45
Total	87	100.00

The subjects taught by the teacher respondents are reflected in Table 7.

Out of 87 respondents, there are 72 or 82.76 percent who teach all the elementary subjects, eight or 9.20 percent teach Math. and Araling Panlipunan, four or 4.60 percent are teaching Science, Araling Panlipunan, and ESP and three or 3.45 percent are teaching EPP and MAPEH.

g. Years in Teaching

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Years in Teaching

Number of Years in Teaching	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	25	28.74
6-10	29	33.33
11-15	10	11.49
16-20	10	11.49
21-25	9	10.34
26-30	2	2.30
31-35	0	0

36 above	2	2.30
Total	87	100.00

The frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to the number of years in teaching is shown in Table 8. There are 29 or 33.33 percent who have 6-10 years of teaching, 25 or 28.74 percent have 1-5 years, 10 or 11.49 percent have 11-15 years and same number have taught for 16-20. There are nine or 10.34 percent who have been in teaching for 21-25 years, and for those with 26-30 and 36 years or more of teaching number to two or 2.30 percent.

2. What is the mental health state of the respondents?

The table below shows the mental health state of the teachers in cluster 6. Data further reveals that 35 or about 40 percent of the respondents are experiencing depression and stress at different degrees as of the time of the study while 52 or 60 percent are in a normal mental health state. Moreover, 60 or 69 percent experience anxiety.

Table 7
Mental Health State of Teachers in Cluster 6

Level	Depression		Anxiety		Stress	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Normal	52	59.770	27	31.0345	52	59.770
Mild	18	20.690	8	9.1954	24	27.586
Moderate	12	13.793	28	32.1839	10	11.494
Severe	5	5.747	11	12.6437	1	1.149
Extremely Severe	0	0.000	13	14.9425	0	0.000
Total	87	100	87	100	87	100

The findings of this present study find similarities with a study published online which says that teachers suffer from depression, anxiety, and stress. Of the sample, 50.6 percent of the teachers indicated that they were suffering from stress, with 4.5 percent reporting extremely severe stress and 14.1 percent severe stress. About 49.5 percent of the teachers reported suffering from anxiety, 8.1 percent of which reported extremely severe symptoms and 7.6 percent severe symptoms.

Finally, 32.2 percent of the teachers reported suffering from depression, of which 3.2 percent reported extremely severe symptoms and 4.3 percent severe symptoms. Besser, et.al. (2002) also found out in their study that teachers have also accumulated a high level of stress since the beginning of the health crisis. The authors cited that during lockdown, teachers have suffered stress from having to adapt (in record time) in order to provide online classes. Similarly, Lily, et al (2020) says that not many studies conducted during the pandemic measure the symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression among

teachers but the studies that have been carried out suggest that they have psychological symptoms and this reinforces the importance of reopening schools and universities. A recent Arab study has indicated that this crisis has caused teachers to suffer problems that are often related to a pandemic situation, such as anxiety, depression, domestic violence, and divorce, all of which restrict their ability to teach properly.

For those experiencing depression in this study, 18 are mildly depressed, 12 are moderately depressed, and five are severely depressed. They claim that sometimes, they find it difficult to work up the initiative to do things. There were those who couldn't seem to experience any positive feeling at all, felt that they had nothing to look forward to, and felt downhearted and blue. A few were unable to become enthusiastic about anything and felt wasn't much as a person and felt that life was meaningless. A meaningless life may mean one is going through an existential crisis and could be borderline depressed. The feeling of emptiness may prevail all other emotions. However, one can be sure that, despite all of these, there's still meaning to one's existence. According to Ho (2021), if one feels that he/she is living a meaningless life, negativity will surround him/her like wildfire. One has to strive to find one's life's meaning to continue to live a life of high motivation

The table also shows that there were those who experienced anxiety where eight are mildly anxious, 28 are in moderate condition, 11 are in severe condition, and 13 are in extremely severe condition. Their anxiety was sometimes manifested by dryness of mouth, worrying about situations in which they panic and make fool of themselves and increase in heart rate or absence of heart beat. There were also those who experienced breathing difficulty, trembling, panic syndrome and worrying without any good reason. According to Oral Surgery of Utah (2020), anxiety and stress can cause dry mouth, and so can the related medications. The body is more prone to acid reflux during periods of intense stress and anxiety, which can negatively impact one's salivary glands and lead to less saliva production. For those experiencing stress, 24 are mildly stressed, 10 are moderately stressed, and one is severely stressed. The teachers who are stressed out sometimes found it difficult to wind down and relax, tend to over react to situations and felt that they were using a lot of nervous energy. There were a few who found themselves getting agitated, intolerant of anything that kept them from getting on with what they were doing, and felt that they were rather touchy.

The data reveals that majority of the respondents were in good state of mental health during the conduct of distance learning mode while there were some who were in a state of depression, anxiety and stress in differing levels.

3. Is there a significant difference in the mental health state of the respondents when grouped according to profile?
a. Depression

Table 8
 Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Depression Experienced by the Respondents When Grouped According to Profile

Respondents' Mental Health in Terms of Depression and the following profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0140	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0062	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0291	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0303	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0735	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0189	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0413	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 9a presents the results of the test of significant difference in the mental health of the respondents in terms of depression when grouped according to profile.

The results show that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 except for the place of residence. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, meaning, there is significant difference in the mental health of the respondents in terms of depression when grouped according to age, civil status, position, number of years in teaching, grade level handled, and subjects handled. It implies that the teachers' feeling of depression differ from each other depending on their age, civil status, number of years in teaching, grade level and subject handled.

The data further reveals that those teachers who are age 41-45, married, teacher II, have been teaching for 11-15 years, handle multigrade, and teach Math/Filipino are on the normal range compared to the rest of the group.

However, there is no significant difference in the mental health state of the teachers in terms of depression when grouped according to the place of residence. This implies that the teachers have similarities in their depression regardless of their place of residence.

Johnson et al. (2005), in his study also had similar findings with this study. He found out that the pattern of depression among the different types of teachers also varied according to sex. For men, being a secondary education teacher in academic subjects, a secondary education teacher in a vocational subject or a secondary education teacher in an artistic or practical subject, a primary education teacher, a special education

teacher, a teaching professional not elsewhere classified or other teaching associated professional or a preprimary education teacher was associated with a greater risk of being diagnosed with depression compared to being a college, university or higher education.

Similarly according to Ho Hossain et al. (2022), they conducted a study that aimed to explore the prevalence of mental health problems among teachers in Bangladesh and to identify the associated risk factors found out that the prevalence of depression was higher among male and older teachers than among their female and younger colleagues. The findings further showed that place of residence, institution, self-reported health, usage of social and electronic media, and fear of COVID-19 significantly influenced the mental health status of teachers.

b. Anxiety

Table 9
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Anxiety
Experienced by the Respondents When Grouped
According to Profile

Respondents' Mental Health in Terms of Anxiety and the following profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0409	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0009	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.1529	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Grade level Handled	0.0417	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0070	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0462	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0492	Reject Ho	Significant

The result of the test of significant difference in the mental health of the respondents in terms of anxiety when grouped according to profile is presented in Table 9b.

The result shows that the F-Probability values are less than 0.05 except for the place of residence. This signifies the rejection of null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, meaning, there is significant difference in the mental health state of the respondents in terms of anxiety when grouped according to age, civil status, grade level handled, position, subject handled, and number of years in teaching. It shows that the teachers have different level of anxiety when they are clustered by the aforesaid profile. The researcher further notes that the teachers who handle multi-grade and teach Math/AP/ESP, Math/Filipino, English/Filipino, have normal anxiety level than the rest of the groups of teachers. While teachers who are of age 41-45 and widow, have mild anxiety level than the rest of the group of teachers. Whereas, those teachers, who taught for 31-35 years and are Teacher II and Master Teacher II, have severe anxiety level than the other groups of teachers.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the anxiety level of teachers when grouped according to place of residence. It implies that the teachers have similarities anxiety regardless of their place of residence.

Being anxious is one of the factors that affect the mental health of teachers nowadays regardless of their place residence and one common reason of their anxiety is COVID-19. The respondents disclosed that whether they are homebased or not, teachers are anxious with all the things that the COVID-19 may bring. In an interview with the teachers, these were some of their fears. *“Alam mo sir, isa lang naman ang kinakatakutan natin ngayon eh, ang makapitan ng COVID na yan, isa pa di mo kasi nakikita kaya doble ingat ang kailangan. Nakakatakot man, pero kailangan naming tatagan at mag-ingat palagi kasi kung sakaling kami ay makakapitan ng virus na yan, di lang naman kami ang magsasuffer kundi maraming madadamay, homebased ka man o hindi yan talaga yung kinakatakutan nating lahat ngayon.”* (There is only one thing that we are afraid of, sir: being infected with COVID. Another problem is that we can't see it. That is why we must exercise caution at all times. We cannot deny that this is extremely frightening. That is why we must always exercise caution, because if we get infected, it will affect more than just ourselves. One possible outcome is that some people will become infected because of our actions. That is what we are afraid of, whether we are home-based teachers or not.)

A study of Ozamiz-Etxebarria et al (2021) indicates that that gender differences emerged with regard to anxiety [$t(1,621) = 4.65, p > 0.001$] and stress [$t(1,621) = 3.94, p > 0.001$] with women showing higher scores on anxiety ($M = 4.28$) and stress ($M = 8.09$) versus men's anxiety ($M = 3.26$).

Agyapong et.al (2022), in their study likewise revealed that anxiety among teachers are correlated with the following demographic variable: sex, age, gender, marital status, years taught/teaching experience, educational level, family economics status and income, work factors/job strain and subjects/level taught.

Furthermore, Arias et al. (2019), in their study cited that teachers working in the earlier stages of pre-school and primary education are those who showed the highest scores on anxiety. This marks a clear difference with previous studies in non-pandemic situation where high school teachers were the most affected by psychological symptoms.

c. Stress

Table 10
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Stress Experienced by the Respondents in Term of Stress When Grouped According to Profile

Respondents' Mental Health in Terms of Stress and the following profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0182	Reject Ho	Significant

Civil Status	0.0461	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.2155	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0047	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 9c discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the mental health of the respondents in terms of stress when grouped according to profile.

The results reveal that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 except for place of residence. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is significant difference in the mental health state of the respondents in terms of stress when grouped according to age, civil status, grade level handled, position, subject handled, and number of years of teaching. The teachers vary in their mental health state in terms of stress when they are classified by the aforementioned demographic profile. It is further revealed that the teachers, who are of age 21-25, married, handling multi-grade level, Teacher III, teaching Math/Filipino and English have been in the service for 11-15 years, have more normal stress level than the rest of the groups of teachers.

However, there is no significant difference of the mental health state of the respondents in terms of stress when grouped according to place of residence. The result further implies that whether one is homebased or not, he/she is not free from the stress because in the education system in the new normal, teachers are adjusting with the modalities, curriculum and instruction that this pandemic has brought. One of the respondents said *“Pareparehas kaming nangangapa ngayon, kasi lahat bago para sa amin. Kailangan naming aralin, kailangan naming matutunan upang maibahagi naming ito ng husto sa aming mga estudyante.”* **(Everybody is struggling, because everything is new. We need to study it, we need to adopt it in order for us to impart all the important information and lessons to our learners.)**

Lai et.al. (2020) in their study reveal that the higher levels of stress among young people (23–35 years), compared with those aged 36–46 years is in line with the general trend observed in other studies, that is, younger people experience higher levels of stress.

4. What coping mechanisms do the teachers employ?

Table 11
The Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Teachers
(Problem Focused)

Coping Mechanism	Mean	Qualitative Description
Active Coping	3.13	A Medium amount
Use of Informational Support	3.05	A Medium amount
Positive Reframing	3.27	I've doing this a lot
Planning	3.08	A Medium amount
Overall Mean	3.13	A Medium Amount

Table 10 presents the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of Problem focused. It shows that the respondents do a lot of positive reframing with a mean of 3.27. They are able to cope with their stress, anxiety and depression by trying to see the situation in a different light to make it seem more positive and look for something good in what is happening. According to an Harvard SDLab, positive reframing involves thinking about a negative or challenging situation in a more positive way. This could involve thinking about a benefit or upside to a negative situation considered. Alternatively, it can involve identifying a lesson to be learned from a difficult situation.

The table also shows that active coping (3.13), use of informational support (3.05) and planning (3.08) are also resorted to by the respondents to a medium amount. The respondents actively cope with their depression, anxiety and stress by concentrating their efforts in doing something about the situation they are facing and take action to make the situation better. Other respondents use informational support by getting help and advice from others, about what to do with the situation. Planning is also done by the respondents to cope with their anxiety by coming up with strategy and steps on what to do to deal with the situation. The data reveals that the respondents deal with their anxiety and stress by focusing on the problem.

Table 12
The Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents in Terms of
Emotion Focused

Emotion Focused	Mean	Qualitative Description
Emotional Support	2.73	A Medium amount
Venting	2.37	A little bit
Humor	2.45	A little bit
Acceptance	3.03	A Medium amount
Religion	3.35	I've doing this a lot

Self-Blame	2.12	A little bit
Overall Mean	2.68	A Medium Amount

The emotional focused as a coping mechanism employed by the teachers is presented in Table 11. The table shows that religion as a coping mechanism has a weighted mean of 3.35 with a qualitative description of “*I’ve been doing this a lot.*” Seeking for emotional support and acceptance of the situation are employed to a medium amount by the respondents to cope with their stress, anxiety and depression with a weighted mean of 2.73 and 3.03, respectively. “*A little bit*” of humor (2.45) venting (2.37) and self-blame (2.12) are employed by the teachers. The overall mean of 2.68 reveals that there is a medium amount of focusing on emotion among the teachers to coping with their anxiety and stress.

The data implies that when the teachers are confronted with anxiety, depression or stress, they always find comfort in their Religion by praying and meditating. It further shows that the respondents believe in the Supreme Being and their faith helps them in handling the challenges in life. This confirms the findings of Halili-Jao (2009) in her study entitled “Coping Mechanisms of Pinoys, that spirituality is the most frequently observed coping style; they stay positive that God will never leave them in times of crisis.

In addition, according to Shelley (2016) both religion and spirituality can have a positive impact on one’s mental health. Both can help a person tolerate stress by generating peace, purpose, and forgiveness. Religion gives people something to believe in, provides a sense of structure and typically offers a group of people to connect with similar beliefs. These facets can have a large positive impact on mental health- research suggests that religiosity reduces suicide. Likewise, Vann (2015) shared that people who pray often and are active with their faith communities might be making generally healthier decisions, such as taking fewer risks or avoiding smoking and drinking

Table 11 also shows that the respondents cope with their anxiety to a medium amount by accepting the reality of the fact that it has happened and learn to live with it. The teachers also cope with their stress and anxiety by getting comfort and understanding from someone, by making fun of the situation and making joke about it. Additionally, the respondents cope a little bit in learning to live with it with a 2.92, making fun of the situation with a mean of 2.37, saying things to let unpleasant feeling escape with a 2.21 mean and criticizing self with a 2.07 mean.

Findings of this study is supported by the findings of HaliliJao (2009) when she stated that Filipinos turn to religion and accept reality in times of crisis She further said that there are some utterances of *bahala na* or behaviors like *ipinapasa Diyos*. Moreover, Halili also cited that the bayanihan or *pakikipagkapwa* is also a well-observed coping behavior by which Filipinos empathize and help each other.

Table 13
The Coping Mechanisms of the Respondents in
Terms of Avoidant Focus

Coping Mechanisms	Mean	Qualitative Description
Self-Distraction	2.84	A Medium amount
Denial	1.99	A little bit
Substance Use	1.30	I haven't been doing this at all
Behavioral Disengagement	1.85	A little bit
Overall Mean	1.99	A Little Bit

Table 12 presents the coping mechanism employed by the respondents when they are anxious, stressed or depressed. The data shows that the teachers employ *a little bit* the avoidant focus coping mechanisms as shown by the general weighted mean of 1.99. One of the avoiding mechanisms they employ is self-distraction where the respondents extend amount in doing something to think about the situation less like going to movies, watching TV, reading, daydreaming, sleeping, or shopping and turning to work or other activities to take mind off things. In addition, the respondents also employ *a little bit* of denial mechanism with a weighted mean of 1.99 such as convincing themselves that the situation isn't real and refusing to believe that it has happened. They also engage in behavioral disengagement like giving up trying to deal with the situation and giving up the attempt to cope. The data also shows that the respondents *haven't been doing* the use of substance to cope with their stress, depression or anxiety like drinking alcohol and other drugs to feel better nor using alcohol and drugs to help them get through the situation.

The findings on the use of self destruction as a coping mechanism affirms Halilijao's (2009) findings that Filipinos lessen their emotional burden by engaging in activities that would relax them, make them happy and feel at easier even if it is just temporary. On one side, the findings of this study on the use of substance runs counter to a study conducted among 781 randomly selected Michigan drinkers. The study mentioned that two motives for alcohol consumption have been emphasized in the etiological and the reasons-for-drinking literature: (a) people drink alcohol to cope with stress, and (b) people drink alcohol because of social influences. This study examined the interactional effects of reasons for drinking alcohol and situational factors on alcohol consumption. Hierarchical multiple regression analyses indicated that gender, friends' alcohol consumption, coping, and social motives for drinking were significant predictors of study participants' alcohol consumption. As predicted, there was a significant interaction between drinking to cope with stress and perceived stress, and there was also a significant interaction between drinking for social reasons and friends' alcohol consumption. Similarly, the findings of the present study contradict Dr. Tan's (2006) statement that people tend to ...or drink their problems away.

5. Significant difference in the coping mechanism employed by the respondents when grouped according to their profile?

Table 14
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Problem Focused
Coping Mechanism of the Respondents when Grouped
According to Their Profile

Respondents' Coping Mechanism in terms of Problem Focused and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0356	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0029	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0011	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0043	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0294	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0128	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0076	Reject Ho	Significant

The result of the test of significant difference in the problem focused coping mechanism of the respondents when grouped according to their profile is represented in Table 13a.

It is reflected from the results that the probability values of F are less 0.05 which signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is significant difference in the problem focused coping mechanism of the respondents when grouped according to their profile. It implies that the teachers have different coping mechanisms in terms of problem focused when classified by age, civil status, position, number of years in teaching, place of residence, grade level and subjects handled. As appended, the mean shows that the teachers of age 31-34, widow, MT2, have been teaching for 31-35 years, and who are handling English/AP/ESP are less problem-focused in coping with their mental health. On the other hand, the teachers who are homebased and handling kindergarten are more problem-focused in addressing their mental health.

Teachers who are handling kindergarten used problem focused strategies because they are handling youngsters. Meaning, they need to be alert and face the problem immediately. They tend to do planning on how to handle the situation. Homebased teachers apply the same coping mechanism because they are near school and there is a possibility that they will act as a frontliner in case the service of the teachers will be needed urgently.

According to Buchanan(2024), the COPE manual states that problem focused is characterized by the facets of active coping, use of informational support, planning and positive reframing. Gaining high score in this coping mechanism are indicative of

psychological strength, grit, a practical approach to problem solving and is predicative of positive outcome.

Table 15
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Coping Mechanism
of the Respondents in Terms of Emotion Focused When
Grouped According to Their Profile

Respondents' Coping Mechanism in Terms of Emotion Focused and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0409	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0152	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0069	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0410	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0053	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0089	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0216	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 13b disclose the result of the test of significant difference in the coping mechanism of the respondents in term of emotion focused when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, meaning there is significant difference in the respondents' use of emotion-focused coping strategies when grouped according to age, civil status, position, numbers of years in teaching, place of residence, grade level and subjects handled.

As indicated by the mean in appendix C, the teachers who are 21-25 years old, widow, MT1, 31-33 years in teaching and seldom apply emotion focused mechanisms to cope with their mental health state. Data also shows that the teachers who are homebased apply more the emotion focused as their coping mechanism to help address a crisis whereas, teachers handling English/AP/ESP never apply emotion focused on their coping mechanism to address their mental health state.

Table 16
Results of Test of Significant Difference in the Coping Mechanism
of the Respondents in Terms of Avoidance When
Grouped According to Their Profile

Respondents' Coping Mechanism in Terms of Avoidance and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0070	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0209	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0085	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0009	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0003	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0205	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0121	Reject Ho	Significant

The result of the test of significant difference in the coping mechanism of the respondents using avoidance strategies when grouped according to their profile are disclosed in Table 13c.

The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level. This implies a significant difference in the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of avoidance when grouped according to their age, civil status, position, number of years in teaching, place of residence, grade level and subjects handled.

Teachers who belong to the age bracket of 21-25, widowed, are MT2, 31 or more years of service, and handling higher grades less apply avoidance as their coping mechanism in their mental health state. On one side, the teachers who are not homebased apply more the avoidance coping mechanism. Similarly, teachers handling Math/AP/ESP and English/AP/ESP never employ avoidance focused as their coping mechanism in their mental health state.

According to some teachers who are home-based, that as front liners in school, they have no choice if they are being called even they do not want to. Others also informed the researcher that they consider themselves as guards of the school and maintain cleanliness but they never complain. They further said that they understand and they tend to cope up with their emotions.

Results of the present study particularly those of Tables 13-a to Table 13-c have semblance with that of Goel and Verma's which explored the workplace perceptions and stress coping mechanisms used by employees of different age groups. Their study found out that stress coping mechanisms differ significantly with age where the older employees scored higher in the use of coping mechanisms compared to the younger counterparts.

6. Significant Relationship of the Respondents' Mental Health State and Coping Mechanism

Table 17
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Mental Health and Coping Mechanism

Variables		Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
Mental Health State	Coping Mechanism			
Depression	Problem Focused	0.4900	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Depression	Emotion Focused	0.3990	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Depression	Avoidance Focused	0.4602	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Problem Focused	0.3730	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Emotion Focused	0.4221	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Avoidance Focused	0.5144	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress	Problem Focused	0.4455	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress	Emotion Focused	0.4434	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress	Avoidance Focused	0.5188	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' mental health and coping mechanism are disclosed in table 14.

The results reveal that the probability values are greater than 0.05. Hence, there is no significant relationship between the mental health and coping mechanism of the teacher-respondents. It implies that the teachers' depression, anxiety and stress are not significantly affected by the coping mechanism in terms of problem, emotion and avoidance focused. It means further that the two variables are not significantly related.

The result of the present study negates the findings in Buizza, et.al.'s (2022) study on coping strategies and mental health of a sample of students accessing a university counselling service. The results indicated that the self-blame coping strategy is a major predictor of mental health issues and that interaction between age and area of study aggravated the symptomatology. Buizza also cited that some studies have found a relationship between psychopathology and coping strategies: for example, avoidance, denial and venting are strongly associated with psychopathology, especially with depression anxiety, eating and personality disorders.

Researchers have also observed associations between coping styles and symptom severity. Lew et al. (2019) found that coping strategies such as self-distraction, self-blame and substance use were risk factors for suicidal behaviors in a sample of Chinese college students. In particular, self-blame was a predictor of stress among college female students, and behavioral disengagement among men according to Eisenbarth (2019). On the contrary, a positive attitude (e.g. acceptance, holding, positive reframing) and problem-oriented strategies (e.g. suppression, planning, active coping) serve as protective factors towards psychological distress and support in promoting well-being as cited by Sica, et.al. (2008).

7. Educational Milieu of the Respondents

Table 18
The Educational Milieu of Respondents in Terms of Safety

Safety in the Educational Milieu	WAM	Verbal Description
How safe is your school environment...		
a. From intruders	2.98	Much
b. From thieves/Robbers	2.80	Much
c. From stray animals	2.61	Much
d. From possible harm/accident	2.86	Much
e. From possible contamination/infection of the COVID virus	2.83	Much
f. In protecting your privacy as teachers	3.31	Very Much
g. In protecting school records	3.47	Very Much
h. In protecting your rights as an individual and as a teacher	3.47	Very Much
Total	3.04	Much

The table above presents the educational milieu of the respondents in terms of safety in school. Based from the table, the teachers perceive their school environment as *very much* safe in protecting school records with a mean of 3.47, protecting their rights as an individual and teacher with a mean 3.47 and protecting their privacy as teachers with a mean of 3.31. According to the teachers, their school is *much* safe from intruders, thieves, possible harm and possible contamination/ infection of the COVID virus. As a whole, they consider their school environment to be *much* safe.

In connection to this finding, the Department of Education's (DepEd) mandate to protect and promote the right to and access to quality basic education, DepEd collects various data and information, including personal information, from various subjects using different systems. In the processing of these data and information, DepEd is committed to ensure the free flow of information as required under the *Freedom of Information Act* (Executive Order No. 2, s. 2016) and to protect and respect the confidentiality and privacy of these data and information as required under the *Data Privacy Act of*

2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). Request for data and information, unless access is denied when such data and information fall under any of the exceptions enshrined in the. Department Order No. 72, s. 2016 provides that only authorized DepEd personnel have access to personal information collected, the exchange of which will be facilitated through email and web applications which are stored in a database in accordance with government policies, rules, regulations, and guidelines.

Table 19
The Educational Milieu of Respondents in
Terms of Support

How much support do you get from:	WAM	Verbal Description
a. Your school administrator in terms of:		
1) a.1 materials needed for instruction	3.09	Much
2) a.2 moral support/motivation	3.23	Much
3) a.3 health needs	3.06	Much
4) a.4 instructional supervision/mentoring	3.36	Very Much
5) a.5 delivery of instruction	3.28	Very Much
Total	3.20	Much
b. Your co-teachers/employees in terms of:		
1) b.1 moral support/motivation	3.29	Very Much
2) b. 2 delivery of instruction	3.57	Very Much
3) b. 3 coaching neophyte teachers and those needing help	3.17	Much
Total	3.34	Very Much
Overall Mean	3.25	Very Much

Table 16 presents the educational milieu of the teachers in terms of the school's administrators and co-teachers' support. Though the administrators' overall support is considered *much*, respondents get very *much* support in the delivery of instruction with a mean of 3.28 and instructional supervision and mentoring with a mean of 3.26. As to the support given them in terms of materials needed for instruction with a mean of 3.09, health needs with a mean of 3.06 and moral support, the teachers consider them as *much*.

With regard the support they get from co-teachers, the respondents revealed that they are very much supported by their fellow teachers in terms of the delivery of instruction with a mean of 3.57 and the moral support given them with a mean of 3.29. They get much support in terms of coaching extended by their co-teachers.

Overall, the respondents are *very much* supported by the administrators and their colleagues as revealed by the general weighted mean of 3.25.

The administration and the teachers are focused on the ongoing changes in the educational environment. One of the key elements that has been highlighted is the need of administrative assistance in addressing the teachers' needs to develop both personally and professionally.

The findings of this study is similar to that of a study of Compasivo & Falcunaya (2020) in Tanauan City, Batangas that evaluated the administrative support and job satisfaction of private school primary teachers. The study's findings show that school administrators support teachers' attendance at seminars, conferences, and training by paying for their registration, housing, and meals. They also help teachers improve their classroom teaching methods and foster positive connections with one another. The survey also showed that school officials allocated funds for the improvement of academic credentials, provided helpful input following classroom observations, and praising the accomplishments of educators. The findings also indicated a substantial link between administrative support and teachers' job satisfaction.

Table 20
The Educational Milieu of Respondents in Terms of Engagement

How engaged are the ADMINISTRATORS in the school affairs in ...	WAM	Verbal Description
1. implementing DepEd/school policies and guidelines?	3.44	Very Much
2. monitoring and evaluation of teachers & student performance?	3.32	Very Much
3. in addressing teachers/employees' concerns?	3.37	Very Much
4. establishing linkage with the community & other stakeholders?	3.34	Very Much
5. in implementing & observing minimum health protocols in school?	3.39	Very Much
Average Mean	3.37	Very Much
How engaged are the TEACHERS in the school affairs in ...		
1. in implementing DepEd/school policies and guidelines?	3.38	Very Much
2. monitoring and evaluation of student performance?	3.34	Very Much
3. in addressing parents/students' concerns?	3.39	Very Much
4. in strictly following minimum health protocols?	3.36	Very Much
Average Mean	3.37	Very Much
How engaged are the STUDENTS in the school affairs in ...		

1. in accomplishing their learning tasks?	3.08	Much
2. in submitting their outputs?	3.15	Much
3. attending online classes/sessions?	2.90	Much
Average Mean	3.04	Much
How engaged are the PARENTS in the school affairs in ...		
1. in assisting their children in their studies?	2.89	Much
2. in giving feedback to the teachers about their children?	2.91	Much
3. in addressing teachers' concerns about their children?	2.79	Much
4. in following school policies on distance learning?	2.93	Much
Average Mean	2.88	Much
General Average Mean	3.17	Much

The educational milieu of the respondents in terms of Engagement is seen in Table 17. The table shows how the teachers perceived how the four groups are engaged in the school activities. The administrators are very much engaged in implementing DepEd/school policies and guidelines with a mean of 3.44, monitoring and evaluation of teachers & student performance with a mean of 3.32, in addressing teachers/employees' concerns with a mean of 3.37, establishing linkage with the community & other stakeholders with a mean of 3.34 and in implementing and observing minimum health protocols in school with a mean of 3.39. The overall weighted average mean of 3.37 implies that the school administrators are *very much* engaged in the affairs of the school which is expected of a school head.

On the part of the teachers, they perceive themselves to be *very much* engaged in implementing DepEd/school policies and guidelines with a mean of 3.38, monitoring and evaluation of student performance with a mean of 3.34 and in strictly following minimum health protocols with a mean of 3.36. In general, the teachers are *very much* engaged in school activities like their administrators.

With regard to students' engagement, the respondents revealed that they are much satisfied on how students submit their outputs with 3.15, accomplish their learning tasks with a mean of 3.08 and attend online class with a mean of 2.90 gaining a total weighted average mean of 3.04.

The parents are also *much* engaged in some school activities like assisting their children in their studies with a mean 2.89, giving feedback to the teachers about their children with a mean 2.91, addressing teachers' concerns about their children with a mean of 2.79, and following school policies on distance learning with a mean of 2.93. Parents' engagement in the educational affairs of their children is *much* as shown in the total weighted average mean of 2.88.

Table 21
Educational Milieu of Cluster 6 Elementary Teachers
In Terms of Connectedness

Connectedness	WAM	Verbal Description
a. Do the teachers show respect for fellow teachers?	3.15	Much
b. Do teachers show respect for the school administrator?	3.13	Much
c. Does the school administrator respect the teachers?	3.43	Very Much
d. Do teachers respect their students?	3.43	Very Much
e. Do teachers show respect for parents?	3.45	Very Much
f. Do parents show respect for teachers in school?	3.52	Very Much
g. Are you welcome and valued as part of the organization?	3.47	Very Much
Average	3.37	Very Much

The teachers of Cluster 6 are *very much* connected with each other in terms of the respect they show for each other and with the school administrators and parents as shown by total weighted average mean of 3.37. Based from the table, parents show respect to teachers with a mean of 3.52, teachers are welcomed and valued as part of the organization with a weighted average mean of 3.47, teachers show respect for parents with a mean of 3.45, both the items teachers respect to students, and administrators respect the teachers gained 3.43 mean respectively. The teachers also show respect for fellow teachers with a mean of 3.15 and teachers show respect to school administrators with a mean of 3.13 or much.

To create effective education systems and effective learning environments, Alomes posits that all stakeholders need to come together in a meaningful way, through collaboration and therefore connection. And successful collaboration between all stakeholders means deep listening as well as active doing. Open, transparent dialogue results in all parties feeling seen, heard and valued, and in the end it's the connection and compassion formed through those healthy relationships that creates successful teaching and learning outcomes. U.S. Department of Education says that when *schools*, districts, parents and community groups *collaborate* and align *their* efforts around student achievement, more students will succeed.

8. Is there a significant difference in the teachers' perception of their educational milieu when grouped according to their profile?

Table 22
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in Teachers' Perception
on the Safety of Their Educational Milieu When Grouped
According to their Profile

Respondents' Perception on Educational Milieu in terms of Safety and their Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0008	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.1547	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Position	0.0367	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0194	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0331	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0265	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0134	Reject Ho	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the educational milieu of the respondents in terms of safety when grouped according to their profile are exhibited in Table 19a.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 except for civil status. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level. As a result, the teachers differ in their perception on the safety of their educational milieu in terms when grouped according to their age, position, number of years in teaching, place of residence, grade level and subjects handled. As evidenced by the mean values, teachers who are 46-50 years old and who handle Grade VI are *very much* satisfied of the safety of their educational milieu while MT2 teachers and 31-36 and above are *not much* satisfied along safety, and those who are homebased and handle Math/ESP/MAPEH are *much* satisfied of the safety of their educational milieu.

The findings also show that there is no significant difference in the teachers' perception of the safety in their educational milieu when grouped by civil status. In connection to this, teachers during an interview said: *"Ano man estado mo sa buhay, single may asawa o balo, ang safety naman sa workplace ang importante ngayon, napakahalaga ng kaligtasan sa lahat ng aspeto ngayon. Dobleng pag-iingat ang kailangan!"* (The safety of your workplace is now more crucial than anything else in your life, whether you are single, married, or widowed. The most crucial factors we must take into account are security and safety. Always exercising caution is necessary.)

Table 23
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in Teachers' Perception
on the Support in Their Educational Milieu When Grouped
According to Their Profile

Respondents' Educational Milieu in terms of Support and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0009	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0015	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0057	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0184	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0203	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0236	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0009	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 19b reflects the results of the test of significant difference in the respondents' perception on the support of their educational milieu when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at five percent level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the respondents' perception on the support of their educational milieu when grouped according to their age, civil status, position, number of years in teaching, place of residence, grade level and subject handled. As appended, the mean values show that teachers who are 36-40 years old, married, Teacher II, 36 and above in service, homebased, handle kindergarten, teach Filipino/ESP are *very much* satisfied of the support in their educational milieu.

The findings imply that the respondents are contented of the support they get from administrators, colleagues, parents and their learners. Working with support brings happiness and motivation. There is a Chinese saying that goes: "If you want happiness for an hour, take a nap. If you want happiness for a day, go fishing. If you want happiness for a year, inherit a fortune. If you want happiness for a lifetime, help somebody." For centuries, the greatest thinkers have suggested the same thing: Happiness is found in helping others according to Santi (2016). Social support is an important factor that can affect mental health. In recent decades, many studies have been done on the impact of social support on mental health. Studies of Harandi et al. (2017), investigated the effect size of the relationship between social support and mental health. People with more positive ethnical social relations and higher social support enjoy more efficient communication skills, which directs them away from depression and other mental problems according to Ghasemipoor & Jahanbakhsh Ganjeh (2010). Moreover, Cobb (1976) introduces the social support as a protector against stress in a way that it largely affects social health and performance. Cobb explains that social support gives people the feeling of being loved, cared, respected, and belonging to a network of communication

Table 24
 Result of the Test of Significant Difference in Teachers' Perception
 on the Engagement of Stakeholders in Their Educational
 Milieu When Grouped According to Their Profile

Respondents' Educational Milieu in terms of Engagement and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0007	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0120	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0013	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0386	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0399	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0073	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0442	Reject Ho	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the teachers' perception on the engagement of stakeholders in their educational milieu when grouped according to their profile are reflected in Table 19c.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 which this signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is significant difference in the teachers' perception on the engagement of stakeholders in their educational milieu when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the teachers significantly differ in their perception on the stakeholders' engagement in their educational milieu when they are grouped by age, civil status, position, number of years in teaching, place of residence, grade level and subject handled. As indicated by the mean values, teachers who belong to age bracket 36-40, married, with MT1 position, 21-25 years in service, home-based, handle kindergarten, and teach EPP/MAPEH, and Filipino/ESP are *very much* satisfied of the stakeholders' engagement in their educational milieu.

The teachers who are in their early adulthood felt that it is very much satisfying if someone monitors them and at the same time they monitor others, too. They see their administrators as someone who they can get some hints to become independent in their own decisions. According to Libretex (2023), many of the developmental tasks of early adulthood involve becoming part of the adult world and gaining independence. Young adults sometimes complain that they are not treated with respect-especially if they are put in positions of authority over older workers. Consequently, young adults may emphasize their age to gain credibility from those who are even slightly younger.

Master teachers who have been in the service for more than two decades said that they are very much satisfied in engaging themselves towards supervision and monitoring as revealed by this statement: *"I already know what I am doing because my stay in the service allowed me experience everything, from traditional to modern way of teaching. I can say that being monitored and supervised by my supervisor is necessary*

for my growth. I would like to admit that I also monitor strictly my pupils and even asked parents to at least be involve in the learning process of their children.”

Kindergarten and EPP, ESP and MAPEH teachers mentioned that there is a need for proper monitoring whether they understand the lesson or module. Kindergarten is the known as foundation age. It is a must that the teacher should engage themselves in the learning process. This is also true to EPP, ESP and MAPEH teachers. These subjects call for a valuing and reflective sessions aside from psycho motor performances. Proper monitoring, supervision and instruction are needed to handle properly the development of the pupils.

Table 25
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in Teachers’ Perception
on the Connectedness of Stakeholders in their Educational
Milieu When Grouped According to Their Profile

Respondents’ Educational Milieu in terms of Connectedness and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0128	Reject Ho	Significant
Civil Status	0.0117	Reject Ho	Significant
Position	0.0003	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	0.0236	Reject Ho	Significant
Place of Residence	0.0071	Reject Ho	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0236	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjects Handled	0.0072	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 19d presents the results of the test of significant difference in the in teachers’ perception on the connectedness of stakeholders in their educational milieu when grouped according to their profile. The results reveal that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 and for this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is significant difference in the teachers’ perception on the connectedness of stakeholders in their educational milieu when grouped according to age, civil status, position, number of years in teaching, place of residence grade level and subjects handled. As appended, the mean shows that teachers who are 21-25 years old, MT2, and with 36 years or more in the service are very much satisfied in their educational milieu in terms of connectedness. Whereas, teachers who are married, homebased, handle Grade VI, teach Math/ESP/MAPEH,EPP/ESP, English/AP/ESP, Filipino/ESP are much satisfied.

The group of respondents who are very much satisfied in their connectedness are in their early adulthood stage. According to an Digital Wellness Lab, during this stage of life, young adults further develop their critical thinking skills, form relationships based on shared values and belief systems, modify their risk taking behaviors and make decisions based on future consequences. As mature adolescents move towards adulthood, these

developmental themes emerge. It means that the respondents are very much engage in their social environment which in turn will bring good interpersonal relationship in their working place.

Being a Master Teacher and with 36 years or more in the service are factors for good engaging endeavor. This is true since Master teachers can really handle smooth sailing relationship because of their professionalism. It counts that they will serve as a good model to young teachers. Thus, they set an example for them to be imitated by people under them. Aside from this, even those who rendered service for almost two decades tend to stay for that long because they already established themselves and considered to be accepted by the working environment.

9. Significant relationship between the educational milieu and mental health state of the respondents?

Table 26

Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Perception on the Educational Milieu and their Mental Health State

Variables		Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
Mental health	Aspects Educational Milieu			
Depression	Safety	0.2725	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Depression	Support	0.1722	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Depression	Engagement	0.2761	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Depression	Connectedness	0.3393	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Safety	0.3129	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Support	0.3704	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Engagement	0.3337	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Anxiety	Connectedness	0.2817	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress	Safety	0.0604	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress	Support	0.2542	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress	Engagement	0.1573	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Stress	Connectedness	0.3938	Accept Ho	Not Significant
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Table 20 exhibits the result of the test of significant relationship between the respondents' perception on their educational milieu and their mental health state.

The results show that the r- probability values are greater than 0.05. this signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' perception on their educational milieu and their mental health state. It implies that the teachers' mental health state are not significantly affected by educational milieu in terms of safety, support, engagement, and connectedness. It means further that the teachers' mental health state and educational milieu are independent from each other.

This study shows that the mental health of the teachers are not affected by their educational milieu. However, the importance of social connectedness in supporting public mental health is well established based on the study made by Saeri et.al (2017). Thus, the reverse causal pathway (that psychological ill-health leads to reduced social connectedness) remains a dominant perspective among mental health practitioners. They aimed to provide a rigorous test of the directionality of this relationship. Results of his study further demonstrate how the psychological resources conferred by social connectedness can act as a 'social cure' for psychological ill-health, and provide the strongest evidence to date for the direction of this relationship in the general community.

10. Is there a significant relationship between the educational milieu and coping mechanism of the respondents?

Table 27
Result of Test Significant Relationship Between Educational Milieu and Coping Mechanism Employed by the Respondents

Variables		Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
Coping Mechanism	Educational Milieu			
Problem Focused	Safety	0.2802	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Emotion Focused	Safety	0.1959	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Avoidance	Safety	0.2946	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Problem Focused	Support	0.0857	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Emotion Focused	Support	0.2900	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Avoidance	Support	0.5424	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Problem Focused	Engagement	0.5468	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Emotion Focused	Engagement	0.5470	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Avoidance	Engagement	0.3810	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Problem Focused	Connectedness	0.4563	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Emotion Focused	Connectedness	0.3952	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Avoidance	Connectedness	0.0254	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 21 discloses the result of test of significant relationship between the educational milieu and coping mechanism employed by the respondents.

The results reveal that the probability values of r are greater than 0,05 except for avoidance and connectedness. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the educational milieu of the teachers are not significantly affected by their coping mechanism except for avoidance and connectedness.

However, there is significant relationship between the avoidance coping mechanism of the teachers and heir connectedness in their educational milieu. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance level. It implies that the teachers' connectedness in their educational milieu is affected by their avoidance coping mechanism.

The connectedness in educational milieu focuses on respect, acceptance and sense of belongingness while the avoidance coping mechanism centers on disengaging from stressors. The findings revealed that the respondents apply avoidance coping mechanism especially if the word respect arises. With this, the respondents tend to keep or not giving attention to how they feel if they are not being accepted by the group.

As per interview, the respondents stated that at times they are not being respected especially if they are talked behind. They even specified that at times they can feel that they are not existing. What is even more hurting is if they are being bullied by people whom they respect much. Asked if they talked already to the bullies, they answered that it is improper since avoiding the issue will save them and even stand as an act of professionalism. So, what they put in their mind for them to get along with the bullies is for them to believe in themselves and the bullies are the one having problems. Seunagal (2021) stated that narcissists bullies are those who choose to bully other adults because they lack empathy or fear of adverse repercussions. Furthermore, they generally struggle with self-esteem issues, hence their compulsion to constantly

denigrate other people. People who truly love themselves don't have to tear others down to feel superior. Narcissists will try to prove how secure they are although their mistreatment of others speaks volumes every time.

In addition, the sense of belongingness is a part of human needs. We need to be with others and our journey of life will evolve because of others. Human behavior is derived by the desire of emotional relations or interpersonal relations at this level. It is a well-known fact that a human is a social animal and he/she likes to be as part of the society and shares common values and belief system with other individuals. It develops a sense of belonging in one or another way. People look for commonality that encourages them to be part of social networks, communities, informal groups, and other social areas. A strong desire for close relations and bonding make friends. According to Maslow as stated in StudiosGuy (2024), humans exchange love, affection and belonging to overcome loneliness, anxiety, depression, etc. One can fulfill these needs through friendship, social activities, family relations, social communities, workplace groups, etc.

The only thing respondents want to experience is for them to be given a room for belongingness for them to properly be motivated to work with respect and happiness within their hearts.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were reached in light of the findings:

The teachers in cluster 6 generally are in a normal mental state showing no signs and symptoms of depression, anxiety and stress except for isolated cases showing mild, moderate and extreme symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression.

The respondents experiencing some depression, stress and anxiety employ strategies that are either problem- focused which is indicative of psychological strength, practical approach to problem solving. Others employ emotional-focused techniques that aim to regulate emotions associated with stressful situation; some makes use of avoidance strategies like disengaging from the stressor.

A positive social and educational environment that gives teachers a feeling of belongingness, being protected, and supported tends to create a relaxed mind, resulting to a positive working environment and productive outputs.

Teachers differ in their mental health state, the coping strategies they employ, and their perception of their educational milieu hen grouped according to their profile.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Administration must review policies and procedures affecting the mental health of the teachers.
2. There should be a continuing education and actions regarding mental health awareness with the teaching, non-teaching staff and the stakeholders such as trainings/forum regarding prevention of mental health issues and promotion of mental health-care strategies and coping mechanisms.
3. The initiatives, projects, and programs that deal with teachers' mental health, such as holding Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions with a mental health theme should be sustained.
4. Research should be conducted on the areas of how coping mechanisms plays in teachers' coping with stress, depression, and anxiety.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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